

Using the Primordial Coupling Constants Function to Derive the Invariance of the Speed of Light & Young Mills Conjecture

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Abstract:

This paper will analyze the coupling constant equation in its first and second representations, net variations and spin. The question analyzed is the invariance of the speed of light. By looking at the process in which a boson is propagating from fermions in each term, we can extrapolate an insight regarding the speed of propagation. Not in a sense of a numerical prediction, but in a sense that there has to be just one speed of propagation.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{0}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N(V)_V + (3) \right) + N(V)_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1}$$

$$N(V)_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{2}$$

$$N(V)_V \in \mathbb{P} \bigoplus (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N(V)_V = P_{max} \text{ in Range } [0, \mathbb{R}] \bigoplus (+1)$$

The second representation of the primordial function using the prime critical line:

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} \quad (3)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} \quad (4)$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} \quad (5)$$

Notice that beside the variation cluster which get bigger, all the interactions are taking the same form. We have the destabilizing factor, which is the electron for example, or the $\frac{1}{2}$ inside the parenthesis, yielding a net variation which is also $\frac{1}{2}$ or prime, according to first representation of the primordial function.

So the propagation speed of all boson of this type must be similar, precisely because there is no detail regarding the speed of propagation and because there is no difference among the bosons, they are all of the same hand. We already proved their dynamical nature by varying the net variations and as a result making them scalar multiples.

Based on the framework of the eight theory, we can make an additional prediction. All bosons of the above type, $2n() + 1$, with no consideration of their mass, will propagate across at the same speed. The same speed applies for all. Even to bosons with mass. That is the young mills problem, how can a boson that carry mass move at the speed of a boson, which do not carry mass.

In the 8-theory the answer is given. Since mass is associated with $8 - 1$ variations, and boons are of the type $8 + 1$ the combination of a boson with mass will not effect on the propagation.

$$8 - 1 + 8 + 1 = 0 \quad (6)$$

The boson that is a mass carrier, causing the matric to converge inward, will be balanced to the other direction by its very nature. As a result, he will move on a linear, not curved trajectory and his speed will not be effected by its mass. In equation six, we took even amount of variations to vanish and so the result is zero. No curving to either direction. Of course, the ideal would be to extract the actual speed of light from the 8-theory. It is currently beyond reach.

The equation does not change under any condition, that means that the speed of propagation does not means under any conditions. In the case of the third element, than, speed of light is invariant to all.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)
- [2] O. Manor. "Proof: The Riemann Hypothesis Using QFT and Lorentz " In: (2021)